

EFFECT PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT, KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND TRANSFORMATIONAL ON THE INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR AND MODERATING EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR ON THE EFFECT OF PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT, KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP ON PSYCHOLOGICAL EMPOWERMENT

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Abstract

This study is designed to examine the effect of perceived organizational support, knowledge management and transformational leadership on innovative work behavior and also to examine the moderating effect of perceived organizational support, knowledge management and transformational leadership on psychological empowerment. The data was collected using a questionnaire using a Likert scale of 1-5 and the respondents were the Secretary and Head of Division in the Regional Apparatus Organization of East Kutai Regency. The number of respondents in this study were 166 respondents. The results showed that 1) the variable perceived organizational support affects Innovative work behavior, 2) Knowledge management affects innovative work behavior, 3) Transformational leadership affects innovative work behavior, 4) perceived organizational support affects psychological empowerment, 5) knowledge management affects psychological empowerment, 6) transformational leadership affects psychological empowerment, 7) perceived organizational support through psychological empowerment affects innovative work behavior, 8) knowledge management through psychological empowerment affects innovative work behavior, 9) transformational leadership through psychological empowerment affects innovative work behavior, 10) Organizational citizenship behavior moderates the effect of perceived organizational support on psychological empowerment, 11) Organizational citizenship behavior moderates the effect of knowledge management on psychological empowerment, 12) Organizational citizenship behavior moderates the effect of transformational leadership on psychological empowerment.

Keywords: Perceived Organizational Support, Knowledge Management, Transformational Leadership, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Psychological Empowerment and Innovative Work Behavior.

INTRODUCTION

The efforts made by the Government of Indonesia to improve competitiveness is by launching the Bureaucratic Reform movement by issuing Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 81 of 2010 concerning the Grand Design of Bureaucratic Reform 2010-2025. The regulation explains that the vision of Bureaucratic Reform is "The Realization of World Class Government". World-class government can be understood as a government that is professional, has integrity, is able to provide quality services to the community, and implement

democratic governance. It aims to m ASN is one of the assets for the bureaucracy which is expected to be able to realize the ideals of world class government in 2024 as stated in the Bureaucratic Reform road map.

In the 5th Edition of ASN Inspiration Talk 2020, it was stated that ASN must be able to prepare itself to face an increasingly complex world in the future, including globalization, digitalization, information technology, competition between countries, information overload, high collaboration, and the challenges we are currently facing, namely the Covid-19 pandemic (Kemenpan RB, 2020). Answer the challenges of the 21st century in 2025 through good governance management.

East Kutai Regency as the largest regency in East Kalimantan is one of the challenges that must be faced by ASN, with this large enough area ASNs must be able to provide the same services throughout the East Kutai regency, in addition to the large budget needed but also needed innovations in providing services to the community there is no gap in the services provided. East Kutai Regency currently has 6,147 honorary workers spread across various OPDs and sub-districts, but according to Government regulations through the Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform (Ministry of PAN RB), it will officially remove honorary workers by the end of 2024.more than 50 thousand people in East Kutai district work as employees of coal mining companies. One of the decisions made by the G20 in Bali is that by 2060, G20 members agree to implement Net Zero Emission. The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources ensures that coal-based steam power plants (PLTU) for the next 10 years can still operate. However, it is certain that in 2050, coal-fired power plants will be permanently closed.

Policy makers such as civil servants are required to be able to provide innovations in policy making that can meet the expectations and needs of the community. Innovation in the work behavior of civil servants (ASN) has attitudes and actions that are creative, innovative, and proactive in completing their tasks and improving the quality of public services. This innovation aims to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of ASN work, as well as meet the expectations and needs of the community. Innovation in ASN work behavior is needed to ensure that public services provided by the government are of high quality and meet community expectations.

Innovative work behavior (IWB) is work behavior that focuses on innovation and problem solving. IWB is work behavior that leads to the discovery and implementation of new ideas and effective problem solving. IWB helps organizations tackle complex problems and encourages rapid innovation and adaptation. Employees with IWB tend to be more creative, productive, and innovative at work and have the ability to cope better with challenges and problems. Furthermore, IWB also contributes to building an innovative work culture and supports innovation and change. Several studies have been conducted on the relationship between perceived organizational support and IWB Hüseyin Aslan (2019) perceived organizational support has a significant positive effect on innovative work behavior, Bilal Afsar & Yuosre Badir (2016) POS has a positive effect on innovative work behavior, Jiwon Park & Woocheol Kim (2022) POS is not directly correlated with IBW, but indirectly affects IWB

through psychological empowerment, Thiery Volery & Liudmila Tarabashkina (2021) Only organizational climate has a significant relationship with IWB.

Good knowledge management also helps to facilitate the exchange and dissemination of knowledge between employees within the organization. This enables employees to learn from the experience and knowledge of their colleagues and use that information to develop innovative solutions. In addition, good knowledge management also helps to build an organizational culture that values and recognizes knowledge and innovation. Organizations should ensure that they have effective knowledge management systems in place to help their employees develop and contribute innovatively. Deviyanti Anggini Putri & Arum Etikariena (2022) innovation self-efficacy has a partial mediating effect on the relationship between knowledge sharing behavior and innovative work behavior. Hafiz Ali Hasan, Jawad Asif, Nouman Waqar, Sidra Khalid, & Sayyid Khawar Abbas (2018) knowledge collection and knowledge provision explain employee innovative work behavior, W. Widodo & Irvandi Gustari (2020) The results revealed that KM and creativity have a source of knowledge From individuals have a positive and significant effect on innovative behavior, both direct and indirect effects mediated by OCB.

Organizations must ensure that they have transformational leadership to help their employees develop and contribute innovatively. Bilal Bin Saida Asad Shahjehanb and Syed Imad Shahc (2019) transformational leadership style has a positive and significant effect on IWB, Bilal Afsar and Mariam Masood (2019) Research reveals that transformational leadership is positively related to innovative performance, Matej Groselj, Matej Cerne, Sandra Penger & Barbara Grah (2020) the relationship between innovative work behavior is an increasingly important phenomenon in today's world of work, including among the state civil apparatus (ASN). IWB refers to the behavior of employees who tend to develop and implement new ideas to improve organizational performance or solve problems faced. Positive relationship between leadership and innovative work behavior.

One phenomenon related to innovation in ASN is digitalization and information technology. In the era of digitalization, ASN needs to master information technology and be able to apply it in their work. This allows ASN to develop innovative solutions and improve the effectiveness of public services. However, starting in 2024 the President of the Republic of Indonesia prohibits ASNs from innovating to create new applications.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Perceived Organizational Support

Perceived organizational support refers to employees' perceptions regarding the extent to which the organization values their contributions, support, and concern for their well-being (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). If employees perceive that the organizational support they receive is high, then employees will integrate membership in the organization into their self-identity and then develop more positive relationships and perceptions of the organization. By integrating membership in the organization with the employee's self-identity, employees feel part of the

organization and feel responsible for contributing and giving their best performance to the organization (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) found that perceived organizational support is also considered a global belief formed by each employee regarding their assessment of organizational policies and procedures. Accordingly, these beliefs are formed based on their experiences with the organization's policies and procedures, receipt of resources, interactions with its agents (e.g., supervisors). Perceived organizational support is defined as the extent to which employees feel supported by their organization's management, including support from direct supervisors. Perceived organizational support is an employee's perception of the organization about how the organization respects and cares about employees. From the understanding of several experts, it can be concluded that perceived organizational support is an employee's feeling about the extent to which the organization values employee work and cares about the welfare of employees who can achieve organizational goals Cullen et al. (2014)

Knowledge Management

According to Dalkir (2005) there are three elements of knowledge management implementation, namely (1) knowledge creation, (2) knowledge sharing, and (3) knowledge application. A company cannot create knowledge without the actions and interactions of its employees. This is where the importance of knowledge sharing as one element in knowledge management to provide opportunities for employees or members of the organization to share knowledge, experience and ideas with employees or other members. In knowledge management, knowledge sharing is an important part that must be owned by the organization. Knowledge sharing is the key to organization success (Wang and Noe, 2010). Lumbantobing (2011) states that knowledge sharing is a systematic process of sharing, and information knowledge from one party to another party in need, through various methods and media. Knowledge sharing is a fundamental thing that must be done by employees in organizations to be able to contribute to the application of knowledge and innovation that ultimately leads to competitive advantage and can create Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) behavior in employees. Knowledge management is a process that can help organizations find, select, disseminate and transfer information that is important and necessary for various activities such as problem solving, dynamic learning processes, and strategic planning and decision making. In a broad sense, knowledge management is a process that coordinates the use of information, knowledge and experience Sykrme (2003).

Transformational Leadership

Leadership is a performance that involves the leader, the followers and the situation. Most when discussing leadership always focus on the personality, physical character, or behavior of a leader while others learn about the working relationship between leaders and followers; others study how about aspects of the situation that can affect leaders in behavior. Directing, guiding, mobilizing, and controlling functionally, starting from the management process at an organizational level, in realizing the whole thing requires humans who are able to influence others or who are called leaders Hughes et al (2015). According to Rotwell, Stavros, and Sullivan (2016), transformational leadership is a style of leadership that transforms followers

to rise above their self-interest and challenges them to collective goals. Transformational leadership is associated with strong self-identification, the creation of a shared vision for the future and the relationship between leaders and followers is based on more than just rewarding obedience. Transformational leaders define the need for change, create a new vision, mobilize commitment to carry out the vision and transform followers both individually and in teams.

Psychological Empowerment

According to Meyerson et al (2008) psychological empowerment is an individual's belief in their ability to carry out work activities related to skills and competencies. Furthermore, Meyerson explains that psychological empowerment is related to how competent or capable people feel empowered in their work environment. Empowerment from a social and psychological perspective is seen as a process of personal growth and development where the qualities, values, and efforts inherent in the individual as well as environmental factors are key. Psychological empowerment, according to Spreitzer is a set of cognitive motivations regarding the work environment and the direction of the individual's thoughts regarding the role in their work (Wagner, et al., 2010). Psychological empowerment is intrinsic motivation that is implanted in the four dimensions of awareness (cognition) of an individual (employee) towards the orientation of his work role, which includes meaning, self-efficacy, self-determination, and impact. There are four elements of empowerment that increase intrinsic motivation at work, namely the existence of opportunities to choose, recognition of competence, meaningfulness and progress at work.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is defined as work that deals with non-binding behavior, is not related to a formal reward system, and overall improves the effectiveness of organizational functioning, in addition, OCB goes beyond the performance indicators required by an organization in formal job descriptions (Bharata et al, 2016). Employees who have OCB will work not only in-role but also extra-role, meaning that employees will not get wages from OCB, a form of extra-role that is done for example by helping other workers in break sessions or leaving early and leaving later than required even though there is no order (Kurniawan & Putra, 2022). The Five Dimensions in OCB are altruism is voluntary actions carried out by a person or group to provide help to others without asking for anything in return, conscientiousness refers to being more cautious and listening to the heart, the dimension of courtesy can be described by a form of action that aims to prevent the emergence of, the dimension of sportsmanship is reflected in aspects of tolerance as well as complaints (complaints) by individuals in their work, Civic virtue is seen from the behavior to participate fully (self-involvement) and give more attention to the company where the person works (Bharata et al., 2016). Perceptions of organizational support refer to employees' perceptions of the extent to which organizations value their contributions, support, and care for their well-being (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). If the employee perceives that the organizational support, he or she receives is high, then the employee will integrate membership as a member of the organization into their self-identity and then develop a more positive relationship and perception of the organization. By merging membership in the organization with employee

identity, the employee feels part of the organization and feels responsible to contribute and provide his best performance to the organization (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) revealed that perceptions of organizational support are also considered as a global belief formed by each employee regarding their assessment of organizational policies and procedures. These beliefs are formed based on their experience of the organization's policies and procedures, the receipt of resources, interactions with its agents (e.g., supervisors), and their perception of the organization's concern for their well-being.

Innovative Work Behavior

Innovative work behavior is a form of behavior that aims to achieve the initiation and introduction of a new idea, process, procedure or product that is useful for the company (De Jong & Hartog, 2010). Messmann (2012) says innovative work behavior is the sum of the physical and cognitive work activities conducted by employees in the context of their work, either alone or in groups to achieve a set of tasks needed for the purpose of developing innovation. While Scott and Bruce (1994) say innovation is a gradual process with different activities and behaviors at each stage. According to De Jong and Hartog (2010) there are 4 (four) dimensions of innovative work behavior, namely: 1) idea exploration, which is a dimension that is the initial stage of innovative work behavior where employees can find an opportunity or a problem. This includes finding ways to develop products, services, and processes as well as trying to think of other alternatives. 2) Idea Generation, which is the second stage of the innovative behavior dimension of work where employees can develop innovative ideas through the process of creating and suggesting ideas for new products, services, and processes. Generally, new ideas arise based on the results of findings at the level of idea exploration. 3) Idea championing, where ideas become relevant when the idea has been successfully created. Because at this stage employees are expected to be encouraged to seek support in realizing the innovation ideas they have generated. Including finding coalitions so that new ideas can be implemented and believing in the success of the idea 4) Idea Implementation, is the last stage of innovative work behavior. In this dimension, employees have the courage to implement the new idea into the process of routine work activities that they usually do. This includes the development and testing of new product ideas, processes and services he offers.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

1. Perceived organizational support has a significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior.
2. Knowledge management has a significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior
3. Transformational leadership has a significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior
4. Perceived organizational support through psychological empowerment has a significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior
5. Knowledge management through psychological empowerment has a significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior

6. Transformational leadership through psychological empowerment has a significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior
7. Perceived organizational support has a significant effect on psychological empowerment
8. Knowledge management has a significant effect on psychological empowerment
9. Transformational leadership has a significant effect on psychological empowerment
10. Organizational Citizenship Behavior significantly moderates the effect of perceived organizational support on psychological empowerment
11. Organizational Citizenship Behavior significantly moderates the effect of perceived organizational support on psychological empowerment
12. Organizational Citizenship Behavior significantly moderates the effect of organizational knowledge management on psychological empowerment
13. Organizational Citizenship Behavior significantly moderates the effect of transformational leadership on psychological empowerment

METHOD

The research method used is a quantitative method. This study used survey techniques by distributing questionnaires. Furthermore, the data or information obtained is processed by statistical methods using Smart PLS software.

The data analysis method uses Partial Least Square (PLS). Based on the data obtained by the researchers, the population in this study is the number of secretaries and heads of fields in the Regional Apparatus Organization found in East Kutai Regency as many as 166 people. Data in this study was collected through the questionnaire method, namely by giving several lists of statements to respondents that were adjusted to the purpose of the study.

The questionnaire in this study was made based on indicators of each research variable. While the measurement scale of the questionnaire is used Likert scale.

Data collection in this research uses primary data. Primary data was obtained from a questionnaire given to respondents with answers based on a Likert scale. Sugyiono (2014) stated that the respondent's opinion on the statement had a value of 5 for each alternative answer of strongly agree (SS); 4 marks for each alternative answer agree (S); 3 marks for each alternative answer netral (N) 2 points for each alternative answer disagree (TS); value 1 for each alternative answer strongly disagree (STS). Data analysis in this research uses quantitative analysis.

Data obtained directly using PLS software. Hypothesis testing uses P Values, namely if P Values < 0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted and vice versa if P Values > 0.05 then the hypothesis is rejected

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

The SEM model development in this study uses SmartPLS through the Structural Equation Modeling Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) method, which consists of outer model and inner model analysis. Outer model in the context of path analysis is a component of the structural equation model used in the Partial Least Squares Path Modeling analysis method. This model aims to measure construct validity, namely the extent to which latent variables are represented by observable measurement indicators. The outer model serves to evaluate the quality of measurement of variables that cannot be observed directly by utilizing observational variables that can be measured directly (Hair et al. 2018). The significance of this function in SEM analysis is crucial because it supports the understanding and validation of latent variable constructs which are important aspects of research (Hair et al. 2019). Outer model analysis in smartPLS involves three main aspects, namely outer loading, construct validity and reliability, and discriminant validity. The following is the development of the outer model in this study:

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha
<i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,924
Psychological Empowerment	0,927
<i>Organizational Citizenship Behavior</i>	0,969
Transformational Leadership	0,984
Knowledge Management	0,957
Perceived Organizational Support	0,949

Sources: Research Finding

The table 1 shows that all variables listed have values above 0.7. Therefore, all variables applied in this study show a consistent level of consistency in each measurement. Thus, all these variables are suitable for use in this research framework.

Table 2: Composite Reliability

Variable	Composite Reliability
<i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,936
Psychological Empowerment	0,939
<i>Organizational Citizenship Behavior</i>	0,971
Transformational Leadership	0,985
Knowledge Management	0,961
Perceived Organizational Support	0,955

Sources: Research Finding

Based on the Composite Reliability value, all variables have a value above 0.700, this indicates that each variable used in this study meets the standard. Therefore, all of these variables can be used in this study.

Table 3: Average Variance Extracted

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
<i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,596
Psychological Empowerment	0,631
<i>Organizational Citizenship Behavior</i>	0,666
Kepemimpinan Transformasional	0,683
Manajemen Pengetahuan	0,624
Perceived Organizational Support	0,641

Sources: Research Finding

The table below shows that each variable has an Average Variance Extracted value that exceeds 0.5. Therefore, each variable applied in this study has the capacity to reflect the latent variables they represent. Therefore, all of these variables can be used in the framework of this study.

Table 4. Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT)

Variable	<i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	Transformational Leadership	Knowledge Management	<i>Organizational Citizenship Behavior</i>	Psychological Empowerment	Perceived Organizational Support
<i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>						
Transformational Leadership	0,250					
Knowledge Management	0,518	0,078				
<i>Organizational Citizenship Behavior</i>	0,137	0,138	0,338			
Psychological Empowerment	0,768	0,165	0,374	0,113		
Perceived Organizational Support	0,492	0,127	0,278	0,074	0,320	

Sources: Research Finding

Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) is a statistical method used to test the discriminant validity between constructs or latent variables in partial path analysis. This method aims to measure the extent to which the correlation between different constructs is lower than the correlation between the same indicators within the same construct. HTMT method involves comparing the correlation between different constructs with the correlation between the same indicators within the same construct. Based on the table above, it can be seen that the HTMT value for each variable is below 0.850. This indicates that each variable meets the initial HTMT criteria and meets Discriminant Validity.

Figure 1: Research Model

The intervening variable Psychological Empowerment is influenced by the independent variable by 0.460 or 46%, while the remaining 54% is influenced by other variables not included in this study. Furthermore, the Innovative Work Behavior variable is influenced by its independent variable by 65.1%, while the remaining 34.9% is influenced by other variables.

Table 6: Q Square

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Psychological Empowerment	1494,000	1081,169	0,276
Innovative Work Behavior	1660,000	1028,742	0,380

Sources: Research Finding

From the table 2 it can be seen that the Q Square value on the Psychological Empowerment variable has a Q square value of $0.276 > 0$, so it can be concluded that the independent variable is able to predict the Psychological Empowerment variable well. Furthermore, the Q Square value on the Innovative Work Behavior variable is $0.380 > 0$, so it can be concluded that the independent variable is able to predict the Innovative Work Behavior variable well.

Table 7: Hypothesis Testing

Construct	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Hypothesis	Description
Perceived Organizational Support -> <i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,223	3,664	0,000	H1	Accepted.
Knowledge Management-> <i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,246	2,595	0,010	H2	Accepted.
Transformational Leadership-> <i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,152	3,947	0,000	H3	Accepted.
Perceived Organizational Support -> Psychological Empowerment -> <i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,095	2,068	0,039	H4	Accepted.
Knowledge Management-> Psychological Empowerment -> <i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,303	3,591	0,000	H5	Accepted.
Transformational Leadership-> Psychological Empowerment -> <i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,094	2,153	0,032	H6	Accepted.
Perceived Organizational Support -> Psychological Empowerment	0,179	2,136	0,033	H7	Accepted.
Knowledge Management-> Psychological Empowerment	0,571	5,250	0,000	H8	Accepted.
Transformational Leadership-> Psychological Empowerment	0,177	2,312	0,021	H9	Accepted.
<i>Organizational Citizenship Behavior</i> x Perceived Organizational Support -> Psychological Empowerment	-0,209	2,015	0,044	H10	Accepted.
<i>Organizational Citizenship Behavior</i> x Knowledge Management-> Psychological Empowerment	0,237	2,929	0,004	H11	Accepted.
<i>Organizational Citizenship Behavior</i> x Transformational Leadership-> Psychological Empowerment	-0,185	2,333	0,020	H12	Accepted.
Psychological Empowerment -> <i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,531	6,561	0,000	H13	Accepted.
Perceived Organizational Support -> <i>Innovative Work Behavior</i>	0,223	3,664	0,000	H1	Accepted.

Sources: Research Finding

Discussion

Based on the SmartPLS output above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The effect of perceived organizational support on Innovative Work Behavior has an original sample value of 0.223 with a P Values value of $0.000 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $3.664 > 1.96$. Therefore, perceived organizational support has a significant positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior and H1 is accepted.
2. The effect of Knowledge Management on Innovative Work Behavior has an original sample value of 0.246 with a P Values value of $0.010 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $2.595 > 1.96$. Therefore, Knowledge Management has a significant positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior and H2 is accepted.
3. The effect of Transformational Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior has an original sample value of 0.152 with a P Values value of $0.000 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $3.947 > 1.96$. Therefore, Transformational Leadership has a significant positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior and H3 is accepted.
4. The effect of perceived organizational support on Innovative Work Behavior through psychological empowerment has an original sample value of 0.095 with a P value of $0.039 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $2.068 > 1.96$. Therefore, perceived organizational support has a significant positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior through psychological empowerment and H4 is accepted.
5. The effect of Knowledge Management on Innovative Work Behavior through Psychological Empowerment has an original sample value of 0.303 with a P Values value of $0.000 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $3.591 > 1.96$. Therefore, Knowledge Management has a significant positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior through Psychological Empowerment and H5 is accepted.
6. The effect of Transformational Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior through Psychological Empowerment has an original sample value of 0.094 with a P Values value of $0.032 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $2.153 > 1.96$. Therefore, Transformational Leadership has a significant positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior through Psychological Empowerment and H6 is accepted.
7. The effect of perceived organizational support on psychological empowerment has an original sample value of 0.179 with a P value of $0.033 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $2.136 > 1.96$. Therefore, perceived organizational support has a significant positive effect on psychological empowerment and H7 is accepted.
8. The effect of Knowledge Management on Psychological Empowerment has an original sample value of 0.571 with a P Values value of $0.000 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $5.250 > 1.96$. Therefore, Knowledge Management has a significant positive effect on Psychological Empowerment and H8 is accepted.

9. The effect of Transformational Leadership on Psychological Empowerment has an original sample value of 0.177 with a P Values value of $0.021 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $2.312 > 1.96$. Therefore, Transformational Leadership has a significant positive effect on Psychological Empowerment and H9 is accepted.
10. The interaction effect between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Perceived Organizational Support on Psychological Empowerment has an original sample value of -0.209 with a P Values value of $0.044 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $2.015 > 1.96$. Therefore, Organizational Citizenship Behavior is able to moderate the influence between Perceived Organizational Support on Psychological Empowerment and H10 is accepted.
11. The interaction effect between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Knowledge Management on Psychological Empowerment has an original sample value of 0.237 with a P Values value of $0.004 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $2.929 > 1.96$. Therefore, Organizational Citizenship Behavior is able to moderate the influence between Management on Psychological Empowerment and H11 is accepted.
12. The interaction effect between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Transformational Leadership on Psychological Empowerment has an original sample value of -0.185 with a P Values value of $0.020 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $2.333 > 1.96$. Therefore, Organizational Citizenship Behavior is able to moderate the influence between Transformational Leadership on Psychological Empowerment and H12 is accepted.
13. The effect of Psychological Empowerment on Innovative Work Behavior has an original sample value of 0.531 with a P Values value of $0.000 < 0.05$, and a T Statistic value of $6.561 > 1.96$. Therefore, Psychological Empowerment has a significant positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior and H13 is accepted.

CONCLUSION

From Result and discussion that conclusion the research, are:

- 1) the variable perceived organizational support affects Innovative work behavior,
- 2) Knowledge management affects innovative work behavior,
- 3) Transformational leadership affects innovative work behavior,
- 4) perceived organizational support affects psychological empowerment,
- 5) knowledge management affects psychological empowerment,
- 6) transformational leadership affects psychological empowerment,
- 7) perceived organizational support through psychological empowerment affects innovative work behavior,
- 8) knowledge management through psychological empowerment affects innovative work behavior,

- 9) transformational leadership through psychological empowerment affects innovative work behavior,
- 10) Organizational citizenship behavior moderates the effect of perceived organizational support on psychological empowerment,
- 11) Organizational citizenship behavior moderates the effect of knowledge management on psychological empowerment,
- 12) Organizational citizenship behavior moderates the effect of transformational leadership on psychological empowerment.

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